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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.725>**DEVELOPMENT OF AFFECTIVE ASSESSMENTS ON
STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN LEARNING
INDONESIAN LANGUAGE****Pani¹, Dina Fitria Handayani²**

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Abstract: The aim of this research is to develop an affective assessment to measure student participation in learning Indonesian. Effective assessment must include emotional dimensions, attitudes and values that support student participation in the learning process. Assessment tools that integrate the principles of polite language skills not only measure student participation and interest, but also ensure that classroom interactions reflect the values of politeness and respect. The method used in this research includes a literature review. The research results show that the developed affect assessment can provide a comprehensive picture of students' affective engagement and positively improve the quality of Indonesian language learning. Active and responsible student participation is expected to support the achievement of comprehensive and meaningful educational goals.

Keywords: Development of Affective Assessment, Student Involvement, Indonesian Language Learning

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Introduction

This article discusses the importance of affective assessment in Indonesian language learning, the development of assessment tools and the results of their implementation, and analysis of the data obtained. It is hoped that this research can really improve the quality of Indonesian language learning in schools.

Learning Indonesian plays an important role in shaping students' character and language skills. Indonesian as the official national language not only functions as a means of communication, but also as a means of spreading the cultural and moral values of society. Student participation in learning determines the effectiveness of mastering the material and applying values. One important aspect of learning is the affective aspect which includes students' attitudes, interests, motivation and values.

When students are involved in learning, they have indirectly shown that they are ready to learn and willing to accept learning. This willingness can be demonstrated through attention, effort, persistence, verbal participation and enjoyment of learning (Rahmi and Salim, 2017). Apart from that, it can be seen how students follow the rules, follow the instructions given by the teacher, focus on learning and are actively involved in it (Kaensige and Yohansa, 2018). Because by participating, students also use God-given relationships to inform their learning experiences (Sari and Appulembang, 2019).

However, in practice, not enough attention is paid to the affective side of evaluation. In fact, students' affective involvement greatly influences learning success. Students who have a positive attitude towards learning Indonesian, have high interest and strong

motivation, participate more actively, understand the material more quickly and are better able to apply language skills in everyday life. Therefore, it is important to develop affective assessments that can comprehensively measure student engagement.

Evaluation includes various measures, such as students' interest in the subject, attitudes towards teachers and classmates, and motivation to participate in the teaching and learning process. By developing appropriate affective assessments, teachers can gain a more complete picture of student engagement and design more effective learning strategies.

The goal of developing this affective assessment was to provide a valid and reliable measure of student emotional engagement. Language Learning Thus, it is hoped that the results of this evaluation can be used to design more appropriate interventions to improve the quality of education. The results of the assessment can also be used as feedback to teachers to improve teaching methods and create a more enjoyable learning environment for students.

Next is the affective domain which is related to feelings, values and attitudes. The independent curriculum divides attitude skills into two parts, namely mental attitudes related to the development of loyal and hardworking students' personalities, and social attitudes related to the development of students' personalities who have noble character, are independent, democratic and responsible. Responsibility is an assessment of emotional attitudes based on an independent curriculum. Moral education programs based on moral law can be implemented with two core values, namely respect and responsibility, because teachers play an important role in shaping students' personalities, but teachers cannot foster and develop them. Student character attitude assessment plays a role and is important in measuring student attitudes, especially responsibility.

Attitude is part of the affective domain. Assessment in the affective domain includes assessment of behavioral characteristics such as attitudes, interests, self-confidence, values and morals. Most teachers don't pay much attention to students' moods when grading. Using a trainer to assess impact areas is inappropriate. The teacher gives a "good" grade if the student has completed the assignment. The predicate given by the breeder must be explainable (rubric). This rubric helps parents understand the real development of students' attitudes.

However, affective evaluation is often overlooked. It is feared that this carelessness could hinder learning assessment to improve student skills. Changing the educational paradigm does not only require changes in the learning process, but also includes changes in the implementation of student learning assessments. Assessments that are limited to certain aspects cannot be used solely as a basis for making decisions regarding student development.

Attitude (affective) according to Bloom in (Afriansari, 2020) does not only include mental aspects, but also includes aspects of physical reactions. So this kind of attitude must have harmony between mental and physical at the same time. If only one's mindset is visible, then the person's attitude will not be clearly visible.

Affective means everything related to a person's attitudes, character, behavior, feelings, interests and values. Affective can also be interpreted as a human ability that is closely related to different emotions or feelings within himself. For example, appreciation, feelings, interests, enthusiasm, values, attitudes towards space, and so on. As Hidayatullah's

research, 2020 states, effectiveness is closely related to attitudes and values. Research conducted (Saftari and Fajriah., 2019) states that affective skills are closely related to interests and attitudes, which can be manifested in a sense of responsibility, cooperation, discipline, commitment, self-confidence, honesty, respect for other people's opinions. Others. And the ability to control yourself.

As research conducted (Marliza., 2015) states that the influence of discipline can be measured by statements that focus on time discipline and following rules during learning. The higher the number of students, the higher the learning outcomes. The influence of a responsible attitude can be measured by statements that emphasize responsibility and risk in activities carried out during learning, so that the higher a student's sense of responsibility, the higher their learning outcomes or achievements.

Methods

The literature review research method is a method used to collect, review, and analyze literature related to a particular topic or research question. The main goal of a literature review is to gain a thorough understanding of the current state of research, identify gaps in the existing literature and identify new directions or approaches for further research. Integrate information from multiple sources to create a cohesive and comprehensive understanding of a research topic. This process often involves grouping studies based on certain themes or concepts. The title of the article developing an affective evaluation of student participation in Indonesian language learning emphasizes the importance of student affective involvement which includes motivation, interest and positive attitudes towards learning. Development of valid and reliable assessment tools to measure affective engagement, including selection of indicators and measurement methods for assessment tools to be applied in learning contexts and evaluation of results to ensure their effectiveness.

Results and Discussion

Results

In affective evaluation, students' good and bad attitudes are assessed using a Likert scale. Where the teacher evaluates students' behavior or attitudes and finds their good and bad characteristics. 80 percent of students have good traits and 20% of students have bad traits. Teachers must deal with students who have these bad traits.

Affective assessment is an assessment method that focuses on students' feelings, attitudes and values. In conjunction with a Likert scale questionnaire, teachers can measure the extent to which students have positive or negative attitudes towards subjects, their classmates and the school environment in general. By using a Likert scale, teachers can obtain measurable and more objective information about student attitudes. The evaluation scale usually ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree with some school officials.

The assessment results show that 80% of students have good characteristics that reflect their positive attitudes towards various aspects of school. However, 20 percent of students have bad characteristics that can affect class dynamics and learning in general. Teachers must have effective strategies for dealing with students who have these bad traits, such as a personal approach, counseling or character programs. In this way, it is hoped that

all students will have a positive learning experience and create a conducive school environment.

Discussion

In the learning process, it is important for students to actively participate in it. Because basically learning is structured in such a way that students participate in it and experience development (Dewi, Ramli and Rinanto, 2018). Learning Indonesian plays an important role in shaping students' character and language skills. Indonesian as the official national language not only functions as a means of communication, but also as a means of spreading the cultural and moral values of society. Student participation in learning determines the effectiveness of mastering the material and applying values. One important aspect of learning is the affective aspect which includes students' attitudes, interests, motivation and values. The improvement in question can be in the form of student grades and improving student attitudes. This development can occur when students have self-awareness, commitment, and involvement with school. In this way, students can be motivated. Being involved in class, paying attention and discussing in class, and being able to show interest and motivation when learning (Reyes, Brackett, Rivers, & White, 2012). Therefore, it can be said that student participation is able to influence students' academic success at school and success in life (Dharmayana, Masrun, & Wirawan, 2012). In addition to student engagement and self-awareness, teacher action is also needed to encourage student behavior.

Assessment plays an important role in ongoing good and effective learning as mandated by the independent curriculum. Evaluation is a systematic and continuous activity that aims to obtain information about student learning processes or outcomes so that decisions can be made based on predetermined criteria (Arifin, 2012). According to research conducted by Afriansari (Afriansari, 2020), the affective domain is an area related to attitudes and values. According to (Juhji, 2020), several experts state that changes in a person's attitude can be predicted if a person has high cognitive control.

The affective aspect is very important because it determines students' behavior and attitudes while studying at school. This affective aspect can be handled by students who have good attitudes such as discipline and responsibility, because this aspect can influence student academic achievement. As research conducted (Marliza., 2015) states that the influence of discipline can be measured by statements that focus on time discipline and following rules during learning. The greater the number of students, the higher the learning outcomes. The influence of a responsible attitude can be measured by statements that emphasize responsibility and risk in activities carried out during learning, so that the higher a student's sense of responsibility, the higher their learning outcomes or achievements. Under the influence of this affective side, students are able to communicate well.

The steps for making an impact instrument are as follows:

1. Select the impact variable to measure. To understand that you are only providing a small target amount to each influence you choose, you must identify the important attitudes, interests, or educational values you choose to convey to students.
2. Determine how many objects to allocate to each affective variable. An equal number of positive and negative statements should be included for each affective variable

selected. Start with at least two elements per variable. If you later decide to add more items to each variable, double the number of items. For example, if you have two targets for an affective variable, you use one positively worded statement and one negatively worded statement. For the four affective variable items, two positive sentences and two negative sentences were used. For certain affective instruments, it is not necessary to add the same number of items to each affective variable assessed. So, you might try to measure some variables with two units per variable, but assign four units to another variable measured with the same instrument. The choice of the number of items required depends on how much you estimate the minimum number of items required to make fairly accurate conclusions about the mood of a group of students on a particular affective variable.

3. Make a series of positive and negative statements for each affective variable. The affect instrument statements are similar to the statements on the Likert instrument. Each of these statements (items) should be distributed randomly throughout the instrument and not placed in identifiable groups related to a particular affective dimension.
4. Determine numbers and expressions of student answer choices. At this point, you should decide whether to use three, four, or five response options to allow students to decide whether they agree or disagree with the statements in the instrument. You also need to decide whether to use traditional Likert responses (such as “strongly agree”) or alternative responses (such as “true for me”).
5. Create clear instructions and an appropriate form of presentation for the instrument. The teaching of affective instruments should receive more attention than is usually given by classroom test developers. Students are often unfamiliar with these affective assessment tools. Therefore, students must understand what is required of them. Remember to add
 - a. At least one sample;
 - b. Ask students to give honest answers;
 - c. A reminder that there are no right or wrong answers in the player.

Therefore, the higher the student's score, the higher the learning outcomes or learning achievement. The influence of a responsible attitude can be measured by statements that emphasize responsibility and risk for actions taken during learning, so that the higher a student's sense of responsibility, the higher their learning results or achievements (Ulfah, 2021).

Krathwohl and Bloom in (Magdalena, 2021) divide the affective domain into five categories, namely:

1. Acceptance/participation/acceptance: this category represents the lowest level of influence, which includes passive acceptance of problems, situations, symptoms, values and beliefs. Receptivity is a type of sensitivity to stimuli directed by the learner or external stimuli. An example is the attitude of students who listen carefully to the teacher's explanation, are ready to accept the values taught and want to join or identify themselves. Operative verbs that can be used in this class: choose, ask, follow, give, fulfill, obey and be interested.

2. Respond/assume: this category involves a response and a feeling of pleasure in responding or doing something that is in accordance with the complementary values accepted by society. Or it could also be said that responding is an attitude that shows active participation, taking part in a phenomenon and responding to it in one way or another. This is illustrated by the timely delivery of task reports. Operative verbs that can be used in this class: answer, help, suggest, compromise, like, greet, support, agree, indicate, inform, choose, inform, order and refuse.
3. Appreciation/evaluation: this category relates to giving value, appreciation and belief to certain symptoms or stimuli. Students not only want to adopt the values taught, but can judge whether a phenomenon is good or bad. Examples are honesty in teaching and learning activities and responsibility in everything in the learning process. The operative verbs used in this class are: suppose, believe, conclude, affirm, determine, initiate, invite, relate, suggest, emphasize and participate.
4. Organization/management: this category involves conceptualizing values into a value system and integrating and prioritizing existing values. An example is the ability to consider the positive and negative impacts of scientific developments on human life. Action verbs used in this class include: try, change, organize, categorize, combine, maintain, build, form an opinion, connect, manage, negotiate and discuss.

Character/traits: this category discusses the integration of all a person's value systems that influence his personality and behavioral patterns. The value entry process is at the top of the value hierarchy. An example is his willingness to change his opinion when there is evidence that does not support his opinion. Operative verbs used in this category include changing behavior, noble character, influencing, listening, qualifying, serving, showing, demonstrating, and completing.

Conclusion

Assessment plays an important role in the ongoing good and effective learning process as mandated by the independent curriculum. Assessment is a systematic and continuous activity in which information is obtained about student learning processes or outcomes so that decisions can be made based on predetermined criteria. Affective skills are closely related to interests and attitudes, which can be manifested in a sense of responsibility, cooperation, discipline, commitment, self-confidence, honesty, respect for other people's opinions, and the ability to manage oneself. The higher the number of students, the higher the learning outcomes or learning achievement. The influence of a responsible attitude can be measured by statements that emphasize responsibility and risk in activities carried out during learning, so that the higher a student's sense of responsibility, the higher their learning outcomes or achievements.

References

- [1]. Afriansari. (2020). Affective Assessment of Integrated Science Online Learning with Using WhatsApp Media. *Diffraction: Journal for Physics Education and Applied Physics*, 2(2), 65–73.
- [2]. Arifin, Z. 2012. *Learning Evaluation*. Bandung: Teenager Rosdakarya Offset.
- [3]. Hidayatullah. (2020). The Influence of the Tandur Learning Model and Adobe Flash Learning Media on Student Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, 3(1), 461–469.
- [4]. Juhji. (2020). *School Public Relations Management*. Bandung: Widina Bhakti Persada.

- [5]. Kaensige, AL, & Yohansa, M. (2018). Using the class123 application as an effort to increase the behavioral involvement of class XII Science students at a high school in the city of Tangerang. *JOHME: Journal of Holistic Mathematics Education*, 2(1), 57-70.
- [6]. Magdalene. (2021). Analysis of Students' Abilities in the Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor Domains of Class II B Students at SDN Kunciran 5 Tangerang. *Archipelago*, 3(1), 48-62.
- [7]. Marliza. (2015). Development of an Affective Assessment Instrument to Measure Student Attitudes *Regarding Values or Norms Related to Diversity Material Live Indonesia*. *Journal of Biotics*, 3(8), 88–89.
- [8]. Rahmi, R., & Salim, RMA (2017). The role of student self-involvement as a mediator in the relationship between classroom climate and the creative attitudes of students at SD Alam School. *Undip Psychology Journal*, 16(1), 77-87
- [9]. Saftari & Fajriah. (2019). Affective Domain Assessment in the Form of an Attitude Scale Assessment *To Assess Learning Results*. *Edutainment: Journal of Educational Sciences and Education*, 7(1), 71–81.
- [10]. Sari, TN, & Appulembang, OD (2019). Application of the drill method to improve students' cognitive learning outcomes in class VII set material at a junior high school in Sentani. *JOHME: Journal of Holistic Mathematics Education*, 2(2), 131-140.
- [11]. Ulfah, Opan Arifudin. 2021. The Influence of Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor Aspects on *Results Student Learning*. *JAA : Al-Amar Journal* Vol.2, No.1